

Generative AI Meets Super-Resolution: A Unified Pipeline for Cancer Imaging

Pedro F. Sousa^{1,2,*}, Tiago Gonçalves^{1,2}, Luís F. Teixeira^{1,2}, Tania Pereira^{1,2}, and Helder P. Oliveira^{1,3}

¹VCMI Group @ CTM, INESC TEC, Porto, Portugal

²Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal

³Faculty of Sciences, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal

*sousa.pedro.fernandes@gmail.com

Despite major treatment innovations, cancer remains a leading cause of mortality worldwide, with breast and lung cancer being the most prevalent. Early and accurate diagnosis through medical imaging is essential for successful treatment. However, the development of robust AI-based diagnostic tools is often hindered by the limited availability of large, high-quality annotated datasets. Acquisition is expensive, time-consuming, and requires input from multiple experts, restricting the training and validation of generalisable deep learning models.

To address these challenges, this work proposes a unified pipeline combining synthetic image generation with single-image super-resolution to produce and enhance medical imaging samples as a scalable solution to data scarcity and quality limitations. The solution is trained and validated on two distinct clinical use cases: breast MRI (Duke Breast Cancer MRI [1] and a private dataset); and lung CT scans (LIDC/IDRI [2] and RIDER [3] datasets). The combined approach is expected to yield image samples of sufficient quality for specialist review and use within the clinical diagnostic framework.

Synthetic Image Generation

For the purpose of stable training and realistic sample generation, we employ a Wasserstein Generative Adversarial Network with Gradient Penalty (WGAN-GP) [4].

Super-Resolution

The upscaling of both real and synthetic 3D images was then performed using a 4x ratio and through a Real Super-Resolution Generative Adversarial Network (Real-ESRGAN) [5].

Figure 1: 512³-Sized Samples produced through the Generative + Super-Resolution Pipeline

A Visual Turing Test involving two radiologists indicated how synthetic slices were mostly indistinguishable from real ones, thus proving the models' ability to capture clinically relevant structures. In conclusion, although some limitations remain, the presented pipeline demonstrates potential to integrate generative and super-resolution techniques to support cancer diagnosis. The proposed framework offers a scalable approach to data augmentation and image enhancement that can be adapted to other imaging modalities and clinical applications.

- [1] Ashirbani Saha, Michael R. Harowicz, Lars J. Grimm, et al. [A machine learning approach to radiogenomics of breast cancer: a study of 922 subjects and 529 DCE-MRI features](#). *British Journal of Cancer* 119, 508–516 (2018).
- [2] Samuel G. Armato III et al. *Data From LIDC-IDRI*. 2015.
- [3] Sg Armato III, Cr Meyer, Mf McNitt-Gray, et al. [The reference image database to evaluate response to therapy in lung cancer \(RIDER\) project: a resource for the development of change-analysis software](#). *Clinical Pharmacology & Therapeutics* 84, 448–456 (2008).
- [4] Ishaan Gulrajani, Faruk Ahmed, Martin Arjovsky, Vincent Dumoulin, and Aaron Courville. *Improved training of wasserstein GANs*. 2017.
- [5] Xintao Wang, Liangbin Xie, Chao Dong, and Ying Shan. *Real-ESRGAN: training real-world blind super-resolution with pure synthetic data*. 2021.

This work is supported by the European Commission funded PHASE IV AI project (Grant Agreement No. 101095384) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, co-financed by Component 5 - Capitalization and Business Innovation, integrated in the Resilience Dimension of the Recovery and Resilience Plan within the scope of the Recovery and Resilience Mechanism (MRR) of the European Union (EU), framed in the Next Generation EU, for the period 2021 - 2026, within project HfPT, with reference 41, and supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) within the PhD grant "2020.06434.BD".